

Research Brief

The Missing Link: How Nigeria's Health Policies is Failing Unemployed and Vulnerable Youth

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NHIA ACT

National Health Insurance Authority Act (NHIA Act) – Mandates health insurance but lacks explicit inclusion for unemployed and vulnerable youths.

Government of Ireland
International Development Programme

THE MISSING LINK: HOW NIGERIA'S HEALTH POLICIES FAIL UNEMPLOYED AND VULNERABLE YOUTH

Youths in Nigeria are the economy drivers bringing economic growth cum development and the Nigeria's increasing population is predominantly youthful with approximately 70% under the age of 30, and with 42% under 15 years old. The proportion of the population decreases with increasing age, indicating a youthful demography (NBS 2022). In 2022, the National Bureau of Statistics highlighted that Nigeria's population pyramid has a broad base, signifying a large number of young people, and a narrow top, indicating fewer older individuals.

This youthful demographic presents both opportunities and challenges for the nation. Harnessing the potential of this young population through deliberate investment in healthcare access is crucial for Nigeria's sustainable development. Unfortunately, majority of these predominant population (youths) suffer from unemployment making them vulnerable to poverty, and worse, health challenges.

DID YOU KNOW...

Unemployed and vulnerable youths are excluded from existing health insurance policies, making healthcare unaffordable.

BHCPF

Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHCPF) – Provides financial protection but does not explicitly define youth as a vulnerable group.

As of 2023, Nigeria's youth unemployment rate stood at 53.4% (NBS 2023), indicating a large population lacking stable income and healthcare access. Also, an estimated 70% of Nigerians rely on out-of-pocket payments for medical expenses (WHO 2022), disproportionately affecting unemployed and vulnerable youth and less than 5% of Nigerians are enrolled in health insurance schemes, with unemployed youths largely excluded (NHIA 2023).

The Nigerian government over the years has made commendable strides in strengthening healthcare accessibility through key interventions such as the National Health Insurance Authority Act (NHIA Act), the Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHCPF), and the National Health Policy. These initiatives reflect a commitment to achieving Universal Health Coverage (UHC), improving healthcare financing, and ensuring equitable healthcare services across different demographics.

DID YOU KNOW...

70% of Nigerians including the unemployed youths rely on out-of-pocket payments for medical expenses?

The NHIA Act establishes a structured framework for health insurance, while the BHCPF is instrumental in providing financial risk protection to the most vulnerable groups. The National Health Policy further underscores the importance of inclusive and accessible healthcare. These policies set a strong foundation for healthcare reforms and signify progress towards a more sustainable and equitable health system in Nigeria.

However, unemployed and vulnerable youths in Nigeria face significant barriers to accessing quality healthcare services.

While the National Health Insurance Authority Act (NHIA Act), the Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHCPF), and the National Health Policy aim to improve healthcare access, there are notable gaps in explicitly capturing unemployed and vulnerable youths under these frameworks. Given that youths constitute a significant portion of Nigeria's economic drivers, addressing their healthcare needs is essential for national productivity and social protection.

DID YOU KNOW...

unemployed and vulnerable youths in Nigeria face significant barriers to accessing quality healthcare services.

WHO ARE UNEMPLOYED AND VULNERABLE YOUTHS?

Unemployed youths are tertiary-educated young individuals who, despite obtaining formal education, are **unable to secure stable employment**. This group possesses qualifications but lacks access to job opportunities due to economic, systemic, or structural barriers. They are **educated yet jobless**.

Vulnerable youths in this context are young individuals **without formal education or vocational skills** who struggle to access sustainable employment. Many are **dropouts** or individuals from **disadvantaged backgrounds** who, due to their **lack of skills** and qualifications, cannot establish profitable self-employment ventures. Their work status is **unstable**, characterised by casual labour (e.g., "**one-day job, one-week/month no job**"), exposing them to **economic insecurity, exploitation, and social risks**. These are also young people living in regions with **poor healthcare access**, young persons with disabilities, and young women facing **gender-based economic exclusion**. These factors heighten their exposure to poverty, exploitation, and limited access to healthcare services.

NHIA ACT (2022) SECTION 14 (1) & (2)

IDENTIFIED GAPS INCLUDE:

Unemployed and Vulnerable Youth Service Uptake and Coverage Not Disaggregated.

NHIA Act (2022) in Section 14 (1) & (2) Mandates that every person resident in Nigeria **must obtain health insurance**, coverage including employers, employees in the public and private sectors (with five staff and above), and informal sector employees. However, there is no explicit mention of jobless, unemployed and vulnerable youths being automatically covered. It does not explicitly provide a clear inclusion mechanism for unemployed, jobless and vulnerable youths. **Are these youths not to be covered because they have no one to pay for their insurance? If they are covered, who pays for their insurance? How is it covered?**

The **Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF)** also **exist to support indigent populations** in session 25 through session 27 of the NHIA Act. The fund is meant to subsidize healthcare for “vulnerable persons” as defined in session 59, but the criteria for disbursement focus on pregnant women, children under five, the elderly, and “the indigent”. These indigents here are not defined broadly enough. They are assumingly the inclusion of amongst others, the jobless, unemployed, vulnerable youths **or not**. This leaves a gap where young people **struggling financially but not classified as indigent** could be left uninsured. **So, what happens to them? Are they technically excluded** due to their vulnerability?

NHIA ACT (2022) SECTION 14 (1) & (2)

Also, In section 27 (2) stating that ***“The Council shall, in disbursing money from the Vulnerable Group Fund make specific provisions towards the health needs of indigents and prescribe the methods for determining who is indigent in Nigeria”***, gives the Council power to decide who qualifies, which means jobless, unemployed, and vulnerable youths **can be overlooked** unless explicitly listed in the criteria. Without a specific provision, unemployed youths will have to **rely on case-by-case determinations**, which can be inconsistent and/or exclude them entirely. Also, within the Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF) framework, there is also **no structured mechanism to integrate unemployed youths into the subsidized health insurance plan.**

Even the National Health Policy (2016) which emphasizes Universal Health Coverage (UHC), it does not comprehensively address the specific challenges faced by unemployed and vulnerable youths in accessing affordable, available, minimum healthcare packages. It does not also explicitly outline how the unemployed youths can benefit from healthcare financing schemes. In a nutshell, **the law and its relevant provisions does not recognize youth unemployment as a basis for healthcare subsidies.**

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GIFSHIP**

IDENTIFIED GAPS INCLUDE:

Systemic Barriers Limiting Youths in Accessing Health Care

Affordability: In Nigeria, different health insurance schemes cater to various groups based on the NHIA Act / National Health Policy, and BHCPF. For NHIA (Federal Level) manages both the formal sector employees (public and private), the informal sector (GIFSHIP) which is available to individuals, families, and groups, and also the VGF targeting the vulnerable populations (where unemployed and vulnerable youths are not included), and ofcourse the State Health Insurance Agencies (SHIAs) which operate under NHIA guidelines.

The Question of Who Pays?

- Formal Sector: Employers and employees contribute via payroll deductions.
- Informal Sector (GIFSHIP): Enrollees (who can) pay premiums out-of-pocket.
- Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF): Funded by the government & international donors.

The problem here is that the **53.4% unemployed (NBS 2023), and vulnerable youths in Nigeria are not automatically covered**, unless they self-enroll in GIFSHIP which is handled by the NHIA at the federal level making it another barrier in capturing youths in rural community and grassroot levels. The self-enrollment in the GIFSHIP where an estimated 70% of Nigerians rely on out-of-pocket payments for medical expenses (WHO 2022), they pay premiums out-of-pocket and must pay upfront to access the healthcare, which excludes them again because **many unemployed and vulnerable youths lack the financial resources to afford health insurance or out-of-pocket payments for the GIFSHIP program.**

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More so, **Unemployed youths lack a stable income**, and unfortunately, many of these types of youths have dependents (aged) who rely on them, exacerbating the difficulty in affording this premium program. Thirdly, unlike the Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF), which covers certain groups in which unemployed and vulnerable youths are not specifically spelt out, **GIFSHIP does not offer subsidies or exemptions for unemployed or financially vulnerable youths.**

For the Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF), the Federal Government administers funds via NHIA Gateway (Covering primary healthcare services), SHIAs (Manage funds for their state-specific schemes), and the Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) (Provide services at the community level). Even though the Federal Government allocates at least 1% of the Consolidated Revenue Fund (CRF), State Governments provide counterpart funding to access BHCPF, and International Donors & Development Partners provide additional financing, the BHCPF primarily covers supposedly “indigents” (based on council criteria), pregnant women, and children under five, the elderly (85+), PWDs, but not unemployed and vulnerable youths. Although less than 5% of Nigerians are enrolled in health insurance schemes, with unemployed youths largely excluded (NHIA 2023). Also, States co-fund the scheme to access federal funds. This means each state’s level of commitment determines how well the program is implemented meaning that **if a state does not prioritize BHCPF implementation, unemployed youths in that state lose out on potential health coverage**, and there are no uniform enforcement mechanism ensuring states follow through, making youth healthcare access highly inconsistent nationwide.

The system is fragmented. While NHIA, BHCPF, and the National Health Policy aims for Universal Health Coverage, **unemployed youths lack a dedicated, automatic inclusion mechanism.** Although **GIFSHIP is an option**, but **requires out-of-pocket payment**, making it unaffordable and inaccessible for jobless, unemployed and vulnerable youths.

AVAILABILITY:

There are gaps in the availability of youth-friendly healthcare services. Nigeria has about 34,000 primary healthcare centers (PHCs), but only 20% are fully functional due to lack of equipment, staffing, and resources (Federal Ministry of Health, 2022).

Most of the available healthcare packages focus primarily on maternal and childcare services, neglecting comprehensive youth-centered services beyond sexual and reproductive health (SRH). **Youths' needs are not only limited to Sexual and Reproductive Health (SRH) services.** Many unemployed and vulnerable youths are prone to other health and accumulated health challenges. Many Nigerians have streamlined PHCs as healthcare that offers immunization and maternal services alone, further widening the gap of availability and awareness of various healthcare services and safety nets for Nigerians especially the vulnerable youths.

AWARENESS:

Many youths including the unemployed and vulnerable youths, are unaware of existing healthcare programs, eligibility criteria, and enrollment processes. There is a lack of targeted outreach and education efforts to bridge this information gap. A survey carried out by DEAN Initiative to assess and understand the awareness level of healthcare service net/packages among community members and young people across various communities in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), revealed that there is little or no information on the various healthcare packages to these people. **Over 70% of youths in surveyed communities were unaware of existing health insurance schemes or subsidized healthcare programs.** If the residents in the FCT lack awareness of these healthcare opportunities, in other states and rural communities, it is likely to be worse. Furthermore, this significant lack of awareness regarding available healthcare packages for youths and community members appears to be a systemic issue. It raises concerns that it may be a deliberate oversight, potentially driven by political motives, thereby limiting youth engagement in knowing and accessing subsidized healthcare benefits.

About 43% of Nigeria's rural population lacks access to a nearby healthcare facility

Minimum Healthcare Packages:

Current policies do not explicitly state a minimum healthcare package tailored to youth needs. While over 60% of youth health concerns go beyond sexual and reproductive health (SRH), most government-subsidized healthcare programs focus primarily on SRH services, neglecting mental health, non-communicable diseases, and general medical care (World Bank 2023).

Proximity:

Many healthcare facilities are located far from youth-dense urban and rural settlements, making access physically challenging especially for the unemployed, financially challenged, and vulnerable youths who still must source for how to get the far-located PHCs. About 43% of Nigeria's rural population lacks access to a nearby healthcare facility, (World Bank 2023). There is also a lack of mobile healthcare units or community-based health initiatives targeted at unemployed and vulnerable youths.

No minimum
healthcare package
tailored to youth
needs.

IDENTIFIED GAPS INCLUDE:

Intended Care Provision vs. Actual Care Uptake

The NHIA Act and BHC PF were designed to extend healthcare access to vulnerable populations, with assumptions of unemployed youths inclusive (although not specifically spelt out) through the Vulnerable Group Fund, but in practice, **unemployed and vulnerable youths face significant barriers in enrolling and utilizing healthcare services** due to bureaucratic bottlenecks, exclusion from automatic coverage, and lack of dedicated funding streams.

Even when unemployed and vulnerable youths manage to enrol in healthcare programs, they often face service delivery challenges, including long wait times, understaffed facilities, and limited-service offerings tailored to their broader health needs.

While SRH services are important, youth healthcare needs go beyond this scope. There is a critical need for expanded healthcare services, including mental health support, primary healthcare, infectious disease management, and non-communicable disease care. **Policy reforms should ensure that healthcare programs for youths are holistic and do not narrowly focus on SRH alone.**

DID YOU KNOW...??

Unemployed and vulnerable youths face significant barriers in enrolling and utilizing healthcare services due to bureaucratic bottlenecks, exclusion from automatic coverage, and lack of dedicated funding streams

POLICY OVERVIEW & GAPS

Nigeria has established various health policies, including:

National Health Insurance Authority Act (NHIA Act) – Mandates health insurance but lacks explicit inclusion for unemployed youths.

Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHCPF) – Provides financial protection but does not explicitly define youth as a vulnerable group.

Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF) – Targets indigent populations but lacks clear criteria for unemployed youths.

No explicit inclusion of unemployed youths in NHIA Act or BHCPF.

ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS

The exclusion of unemployed and vulnerable youths from healthcare packages hinders workforce productivity, increases emergency medical costs, and escalates fiscal pressure on social welfare programs.

SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS:

Limited healthcare access for unemployed and vulnerable youths leads to deteriorating health, entrenched poverty, and heightened risks of substance abuse, crime, and societal instability.

THE CONSEQUENCES OF EXCLUDING UNEMPLOYED AND VULNERABLE YOUTHS FROM HEALTHCARE PACKAGES

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPLICATIONS

Poor health among youths reduces participation in environmental and community initiatives while exacerbating the spread of infectious diseases, threatening public health and sanitation.

Youths are not automatically covered in NHIA or BHC PF, and premium costs are prohibitive.

Implications of Excluding Unemployed and Vulnerable Youths from Healthcare Packages

- **Economic Implications:** Unemployed and vulnerable youths with untreated health issues struggle to contribute effectively to the workforce, weakening Nigeria's economic growth. Also, lack of preventive healthcare leads to increased emergency medical expenses, burdening both individuals and the national healthcare system, and without well-defined strategic healthcare access, more young people will continually rely on government relief programs, increasing fiscal pressure on social welfare budgets.
- **Social Implications:** Exclusion from healthcare leads to worsening health conditions, lower life expectancy, and an increased burden of disease among young people. Also, vulnerable and unemployed youths experience greater health disparities, limiting their ability to escape poverty. More so, health insecurity can contribute to substance abuse, increased crime rates, and instability in communities.
- **Environmental Implications:** Unhealthy youths are less able to participate in climate action, environmental programs, or community development initiatives and inadequate healthcare access exacerbates the spread of infectious diseases, impacting public health and environmental sanitation.

GLOBAL BEST PRACTICES

COUNTRY APPROACH

Germany

Government-subsidized health insurance for unemployed youths.

France

Universal health protection through tax-based funding.

Thailand

Free healthcare under Universal Coverage Scheme

Ireland

The Inclusion Health Framework (2024) by the Department of Health integrates inclusion health principles into national policies to address health disparities and ensure equitable healthcare access for marginalized, unemployed, and vulnerable youths.

Rwanda

Community-based health insurance with subsidized premiums.

Ghana

NHIS includes unemployed under an indigent exemption policy.

GLOBAL BEST PRACTICES AND RECOMMENDATION

Many countries have successfully implemented health insurance as a social protection measure for youths, ensuring comprehensive healthcare coverage regardless of employment status. Nigeria can learn from these models:

Germany - Statutory Health Insurance (SHI): Provides universal health coverage, including unemployed youths, with government-subsidized plans for those without income. Nigeria can expand NHIA's Vulnerable Group Fund to explicitly include unemployed youths, ensuring they receive automatic subsidies.

France - Universal Health Protection (PUMa): Ensures all residents, including unemployed youths, receive free or subsidized healthcare through tax-based funding. The Nigerian government can introduce a youth-targeted social protection policy that guarantees state-funded health insurance for unemployed individuals.

Thailand - Universal Coverage Scheme (UCS): Provides free healthcare to all citizens, including unemployed youths, without premium payments. Nigeria could develop a Youth Health Safety Net Program under NHIA, funded through VAT allocations and international donor contributions.

Ghana - National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS): Covers unemployed and vulnerable populations under an indigent exemption policy funded by VAT and payroll deductions. Nigeria could adopt a VAT-supported youth health fund and link health insurance to youth employment and skills development programs.

Rwanda - Mutuelle de Santé: Provides community-based health insurance, ensuring all unemployed individuals can access healthcare through subsidised premiums. Nigeria can introduce community-based youth health insurance programs integrated into SHIAs to cover grassroots populations.

Ireland - Inclusion Health and Community-Based Healthcare: The Government of Ireland has implemented inclusive healthcare policies in addition to supporting the “Youth Health Access” project by the DEAN Initiative, to ensure that vulnerable and unemployed individuals, including youth, have access to healthcare services. Their intervention focused on reducing health inequalities through policy reforms, community-based programs, and targeted social protection measures. There is the Inclusion Health Framework (2024), established by the Department of Health, aims to integrate inclusion health principles into their national policies in addressing health disparities among marginalised groups, ensuring that unemployed and vulnerable youths receive equitable access to healthcare. Secondly is the Sláintecare Healthy Communities Programme (2021), an initiative that provides health and wellbeing services in disadvantaged communities strengthening community-based healthcare and ensuring that low-income and unemployed individuals have access to preventive and primary healthcare services without financial hardship. Nigeria can adapt similar strategies by incorporating unemployed and vulnerable youths explicitly into healthcare financing policies such as the NHIA Act and BHCPF, ensuring that they receive automatic coverage and subsidies.

KEY RECOMMENDED STRATEGIES

✓ Expand the Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF): Modify NHIA Act to explicitly include unemployed youths.
 ✓ Create a Dedicated Youth Health Fund: Allocate 1% of VAT revenue to finance youth health insurance.
 ✓ Decentralized Enrollment: Enable automatic registration of unemployed youths via digital platforms and community programs.
 ✓ Expand Health Packages: Include mental health services, chronic disease care, and youth-focused healthcare needs.

IMMEDIATE NEXT STEPS

- Expansion of the Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF) within NHIA: Modify and amend the NHIA Act Section 27 to explicitly include unemployed and vulnerable youths under the Vulnerable Group Fund, **ensuring automatic inclusion in NHIA programs upon completion of secondary/vocational education.**
- Youth Health Awareness Campaigns: Launch targeted information programs at universities, vocational centers, and community hubs to improve youth participation in health insurance schemes.
- Decentralized Enrollment: **Enable automatic registration of unemployed youths** through digital platforms, state health insurance schemes (SHIAs), and community outreach programs.

OTHER STEPS

- Dedicated Youth Health Fund: Dedicate or include **1% of VAT revenue to fund youth health insurance** as a social protection strategy
- Expand Health Packages Beyond SRH: Ensure NHIA and BHCPF include mental health services, chronic disease care, and primary healthcare tailored to youth needs.

KEY POLICY GAPS IN YOUTH HEALTH ACCESS

Policy Area	Identified Gaps	Implications	Recommendations
NHIA Act (2022)	No explicit inclusion of unemployed and vulnerable youth in mandatory health insurance coverage.	Many young people remain uninsured and cannot afford healthcare.	Amend NHIA Act to explicitly list unemployed youth under the Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF).
Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF)	Focuses on pregnant women, children under five, and the elderly; unemployed youth not explicitly included.	Youths without income are left without financial support for health services.	Broaden the definition of "indigents" to include unemployed and vulnerable youths.
Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF)	No structured mechanism to integrate unemployed youth into subsidized health plans.	Health coverage is inconsistent across states, leading to disparities.	Establish a Youth Health Safety Net Program funded through VAT and donor contributions.
GIFSHIP (Government Individual & Family Social Health Insurance Program)	Requires out-of-pocket premium payments, making it unaffordable for jobless youth.	Excludes those who lack financial means, increasing healthcare inaccessibility.	Introduce subsidized or zero-cost enrollment for unemployed and vulnerable youth.
Health Service Availability	Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) are distant and poorly equipped for youth-specific health needs.	Lack of mental health services, youth-centered primary care, and essential healthcare beyond sexual and reproductive health (SRH).	Establish youth-friendly health hubs and mobile healthcare units in underserved regions.

RECOMMENDED FUNDING STRATEGY

The recent increase in taxation in Nigeria has led to widespread public concern and dissatisfaction. Many Nigerians are questioning the allocation and transparency of tax revenues. However, by adopting a tax-driven strategy for youth health insurance inclusion, citizens can see exactly how their tax contributions are being utilised for a meaningful cause.

Dedicating 1% of VAT on consumables to a Youth Health Insurance Fund would provide a sustainable financial mechanism to support healthcare access for unemployed and vulnerable youth. This approach ensures that taxpayers can trace the direct impact of their contributions, making it a socially beneficial and publicly accepted policy intervention. Instead of facing resistance, this targeted tax allocation would be embraced, as it delivers tangible benefits to millions of young Nigerians.

Moreso, engaging corporate organisations, banks, and development agencies to co-finance youth health insurance under Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, encouraging telecom and fintech companies to integrate micro-health insurance contributions into digital payment platforms.

Conclusion

Ensuring comprehensive health coverage for unemployed and vulnerable youths is essential for Nigeria's economic stability, public health resilient, and social protection framework. By adopting global best practices, amending existing policies, and introducing youth-centered healthcare financing, Nigeria can bridge the healthcare access gap and empower its young population for a healthier future.

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MAKE YOUTH HEALTH COUNT

GAPS IN ADVANCING YOUTH HEALTH ACCESS IN NIGERIA

Key Statistics:

- Unemployment Rate (2023): 53.4% (NBS 2023)
- Health Insurance Coverage: Less than 5% of Nigerians are insured (NHIA 2023)
- Out-of-pocket Healthcare Spending: 70% of Nigerians pay medical bills out-of-pocket (WHO 2022)

Challenge: Unemployed and vulnerable youths are often excluded from existing health insurance policies, making healthcare unaffordable.

Policy Overview & Gaps

Nigeria has established various health policies, including:

- National Health Insurance Authority Act (NHIA Act) – Mandates health insurance but lacks explicit inclusion for unemployed youths.
- Basic Healthcare Provision Fund (BHC PF) – Provides financial protection but does not explicitly define youth as a vulnerable group.

Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF) – Targets indigent populations but lacks clear criteria for unemployed youths.

Identified Gaps:

- ✓ No explicit inclusion of unemployed youths in NHIA Act or BHC PF.
- ✓ Health insurance schemes require self-enrollment with upfront payments.
- ✓ Limited youth-friendly healthcare services beyond reproductive health.
- ✓ Lack of awareness and outreach for youth healthcare programs.
- ✓ No minimum healthcare package tailored to youth needs.
- ✓ Geographical barriers—health facilities are distant from youth-dense areas.

Key Recommended Strategies

- ✓ Expand the Vulnerable Group Fund (VGF): Modify NHIA Act to explicitly include unemployed youths.
- ✓ Create a Dedicated Youth Health Fund: Allocate 1% of VAT revenue to finance youth health insurance.
- ✓ Decentralized Enrollment: Enable automatic registration of unemployed youths via digital platforms and community programs.
- ✓ Expand Health Packages: Include mental health services, chronic disease care, and youth-focused healthcare needs.
- ✓ Youth Health Awareness Campaigns: Improve outreach through universities, vocational centers, and media.
- ✓ Corporate & CSR Engagement: Encourage private sector partnerships to fund youth health programs.

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